

MODEL OF TEACHERS COMPETENCE IN GENDER EDUCATION OF PRESCHOOL CHILDRE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11390783>

Abstract. *At any time in a person's life, his parents and teachers set an example for him as a person. For this reason, many from childhood imitate adults in their behavior. This attitude affects the character of the child, his life positions, behavior, attitude to people, in general, the formation of his personality. Preschool age is the most important stage in a person's development. This is the period of the child's first socialization, his entry into the world of culture, the world of universal values; The leading areas of this being are the world of people, the world of things, the natural world, and the time to establish an initial relationship with one's own inner world*

Keywords: Gender education, competence, education, integration, socialization, development.

МОДЕЛЬ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ ПЕДАГОГА В ГЕНДЕРНОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ ДЕТЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНИКА

Аннотация. *В любой момент жизни человека его родители и учителя подают ему пример как личности. По этой причине многие с детства подражают взрослым в своем поведении. Такое отношение влияет на характер ребенка, его жизненные позиции, поведение, отношение к людям, в целом на формирование его личности. Дошкольный возраст – важнейший этап в развитии человека. Это период первой социализации ребенка, его вхождения в мир культуры, мир общечеловеческих ценностей; Ведущими областями этого бытия являются мир людей, мир вещей, мир природы и время установления первоначальных отношений с собственным внутренним миром.*

Ключевые слова: Гендерное образование, компетентность, образование, интеграция, социализация, развитие.

Introduction. *Professional competence in the field of gender education of preschool children– this is an integrative personal characteristic (description) that includes the gender culture of society and the system of knowledge about the gender characteristics of the subjects in the educational process, valuable ideas about the development of the individual from the point of view of his gender characteristics, the skills of successfully applying this knowledge in practical activities and on the basis of this, it includes the formation of subjective experience in solving professional and personal tasks, which are considered important in the performance of professional activities in the field of gender education.*

The relevance of gender education is also related to the fact that local pedagogy is mainly focused on the psychological and age characteristics of the child, although many teachers have already begun to take into account the difference in psychophysiological characteristics, intellectual abilities and methods.

Psychological and pedagogical competence In our research, we have analyzed the system of knowledge in the field of gender psychology and pedagogy, persistent interest in modern educational programs related to gender education of preschool children, skills and competencies

for working with methods and technologies of gender education, socialization of children in the conditions of preschool education organization. is defined as an integrative personal characteristic, which includes the ability to perform activities related to the solution of professional tasks related to pedagogical monitoring. These changes caused the emergence of new state educational standards, which became the main direction in the professional activity of pedagogues.

Analysis of literature on the topic(Literature review). Research reflecting the essence and uniqueness of gender socialization in preschool childhood (L.V. Gradusova, Y.S. Grigoryeva, L.V. Kolomichenko, N.E. Tatarinseva)[1], as well as research on personality integration, characteristics of the manifestation of gender characteristics of a socialized person (O. Weinenger , D.V. Kolesov, A. Maslow, K. Rodgers) [2]

I.A.Zimnyaya, In accordance with the scientific approach of D.A. Meshcheryakov and V. Hutmacher, in the structure of psychological-pedagogical and socio-cultural competencies, we have distinguished the main competencies: informative, motivational, operational and reflexive. Studying the features of the future pedagogical activity of educators requires turning to the phenomenological analysis of the concept of "gender education" as a goal-oriented process of gender socialization in the cultural space of society.[3] As one of the initial methodological positions in the analysis of fundamental works in the field of gender socialization (T.A.Repina, I.S.Kon) in our research, we accept the fact that the process of social development of an individual in the space of gender culture takes place on the basis of the choice of the model and formation of the stereotype of behavior by the student in intercultural interaction allowed to do.[4] This process requires specially organized conditions in the organization of preschool education and is implemented in the context of gender education (L.V. Gradusova, Y.S. Grigoryeva, N.E. Tatarinseva, etc.)[1,9].

B. G. Ananyev, N. V. Kuzmina, A. A. Rean, V. A. Slastenin's research on the study of the uniqueness of the personal and mental development of students as a specific socio-psychological and age-related category tells us: the intellectual and social maturity of this age group , to determine a number of psychological priorities, which are manifested in the mutual harmony of cognition and communicative activity, self-awareness, the development of the motivational circle (achievement motive and knowledge motive), and the direction of the individual, and future educators made it possible to put forward the assumption that it is possible to effectively develop the professional competence of preschool children in the field of gender education, to design a systematic-structural model of its development (Fig. 1) in accordance with the research tasks.

Research Methodology.

Supporting the position of L.I.Novikova, A.T.Kuratkin, it can be said that the proposed model is a system of interconnected elements in the process of developing the professional competence of future teachers in the field of gender education of preschool children, presented in the form of technological process blocks. based on the minimum number of the main stages. This model is based on competent, cultural and systematic methodological approaches.[5]

External environment In relation to the technology we are designing, it is presented according to the social order of children in the society to a specialist with competences in gender education issues, the main representatives of this environment are the leaders of preschool organizations and the community of students interested in gender education issues. Changes in the

content of education open up new opportunities for individual development at each stage of the educational system. The motivational-objective block of this model envisages the study of the external and internal environment that affects the development of professional competence of future teachers.

MODEL of important constituent components in the development of professional competence of educators

Figure 1. A structural model for the development of professional competence of future educators in the field of gender education of preschool children

The external environment is presented according to the social order of the children in the society to the specialist who has competences in gender education issues in relation to the technology we are designing, the main representatives of this environment are the leaders of preschool organizations and the community of students interested in gender education issues. The motivational-objective block of this model envisages the study of the external and internal environment that affects the development of professional competence of future teachers.

Also to the *external environment* the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", on the approval of the State Standard of Preschool Education and Education, the concept of development of the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 on approval. The decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the decision of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis on the approval of the strategy for achieving gender equality in the Republic of Uzbekistan by 2030, and scientific developments in the field of pedagogy and psychology are also included. Students studying in the 2nd year of the technology of development of professional competence of preschool children in the field of gender education, together with their general cultural and general professional competences, as well as age-related and socio-psychological characteristics that prepare the foundations for the internal environment of the system falls. Later, general cultural and general professional competences serve as a basis for the development of socio-cultural and psychological-pedagogical competences.

The motivational-objective block of the model includes: the main goal of the technology is to develop the professional competence of future teachers in the field of gender education of preschool children to an optimal level, the principles on which the technology is based and the definition of the main methodological approaches (competent, cultural and systematic). The principles of scientificity, universality, systematicity, cultural compatibility, integration and "dialogue of cultures", principles related to the humanistic paradigm of teaching (co-development, acceptance, unity, freedom, equality and dialogism) are the main principles in the implementation of the designed technology. The content block includes the psychological-pedagogical monitoring (accompaniment) program "Psychological-pedagogical and socio-cultural aspects (aspects) of the formation of professional competence of future educators in the field of gender education of preschool children". This program consists of two educational modules: "I am in the world of gender culture" and "I am in the world of teaching profession". Each module consists of 5 topics; modules can be mastered in the desired sequence, but the sequence of topics in each module should not be changed, because the delivery of theoretical knowledge is based on the principle of concentration and complexity of theoretical material. The program is intended for full-time and part-time students studying pedagogy and its total volume is 72 hours.

Studying the features of the future pedagogical activity of educators requires turning to the phenomenological analysis of the concept of "gender education" as a goal-oriented process of gender socialization in the cultural space of society. As one of the initial methodological positions in the analysis of fundamental works in the field of gender socialization (T.A.Repina, I.S.Kon) in our research, we accept the fact that the process of social development of an individual in the space of gender culture takes place on the basis of the choice of the model and formation of the stereotype of behavior by the student in intercultural interaction allowed to do.[6] This process in the

preschool education organization requires specially organized conditions and is implemented in the context of gender education.

Analysis and results. As T.A. Kulikova noted, the problem of gender development and education in modern society is very acute. The flow of information, its "openness" for children thanks to television, rightly worries both teachers and psychologists. This information does not lead to an increase in the level of adult culture, it is necessary for the gender education of children.

The conditions for effective implementation of technology are as follows:

- to determine the results of the development of the professional competence of future teachers by studying the dynamics of the development of psychological-pedagogical and socio-cultural competences;

- application of active and problem-based methods (methods) of teaching on the basis of variable combination with pedagogical technologies such as art therapy and fairy-tale therapy;

- taking into account the principles of scientificity, universality (lightness), systematicity, cultural compatibility and "dialogue of cultures" in the organization of the pedagogical process, as well as the principles of psychological and pedagogical support for the individual in the educational space (acceptance, co-development, freedom, dialogism, unity, equality).[3]

Gender development and education is considered as the moral formation of a person. It is aimed at forming a holistic personality of boys and girls who can understand the anatomical and physiological characteristics of the sexes and their social roles in life.

Lack of knowledge and inability to deal with children, as well as not understanding the specifics of childhood experience, adults often unknowingly cause psychological damage to children, deform them, and thus lead to the development of basic development. to destroy the drivers and their entire further life line.

Children understand gender stereotypes in preschool and their understanding grows throughout a person's life.

Today's children are the future of the country. The future of children and the country depends on many factors. One thing is certain: the well-being of Russian citizens is possible only in a civilized legal state. One of the most important tasks is to form ethical and legal practices based on values in the interests of children. This means that the material and other benefits necessary for the child's life and all-round development should be provided in full at every age. A child deprived of care and attention does not have a second chance for normal growth and healthy development, so the problem of child protection at all levels should be given primary attention Edited by L.N. Voloshina; speaker: L.V. Trubaichuk, S.A. Khaustova: Actual problems of preschool education. - Belgorod: GiK, 2011 .. Preschool education and education is the first and main social and state form of professional pedagogical work with the young generation. The main qualities of a person are formed in the first years of life. This, in fact, determines the socio-cultural importance of preschool education along with the family form of education.

In the following years, serious attempts were made to reform preschool education, and its conceptual foundations were defined. The turning of the preschool education organization to the child, his requests and individual development is possible only with the implementation of new principles of management and high professional skills of its leaders.

In order to ensure the quality of preschool education, the professional level of teachers working in the educational organization that implements the basic general education program of preschool education is important. Federal state educational standard, 2014 Volosovets T.V.

The creation of a modern preschool education system implies a double specialization of the employees of this service: the first takes care of the child, forms his choice of the most important habits of life and activity; the second is to ensure the development of the entire spectrum of the child's abilities.

Preschool education assumes the presence of a culturally enriched developmental environment, as opposed to a narrow pragmatic intellectualization of the child's entire development.

Due to its important features, pre-school education has a special feature that should be taken into account when solving problems related to its reform. Certain features of the regulation of preschool education are reflected in regulatory legal documents, in particular, in the Law of the Russian Federation "On Education".

- is a type of educational organization that implements the basic general educational program of preschool education.

Preschool educational organization has its specific characteristics: goals, team structure, types and content of information and communication processes.

The tasks of the preschool educational organization are to fully satisfy the needs of the family and society for the care of children, their development and education.

Management of a preschool education organization should be understood as a purposeful activity that ensures the consistency of the joint work of employees in solving the problems of raising children at the level of modern requirements. Federal state educational standard, 2014 Volosovets T.V..

The organizational structure of management in a preschool educational organization is a set of all bodies with specific functions. It can be expressed in the form of two main substructures - administrative and state management.

The organizational activity of the manager should be aimed at ensuring comprehensive education and development of each child. It can be divided into: constructive-design, communicative, organizational and gnostic components.

The structural and design component includes the planning of organizational and pedagogical activities of the entire team. This includes planning the content of kindergarten work: drawing up estimates and other planning and financial documents, tariff lists, distribution of work on time and among team members; creating conditions for their interaction in the work process

The real organizational activity of the leader is the ability to find various interactions so that the results of the joint activities of the kindergarten staff correspond to the goals and tasks of the preschool education organization. The head, together with the teachers, chooses the program of working with children, ensures and supervises the work of pedagogues and medical workers for its implementation, organizes the pedagogical universal education of parents, and the professional development of teachers.

The manager's communicative activity is aimed at establishing the right relationship between team members, taking into account their individual and age characteristics. At the same time, he should connect his activities with the requirements of the leader.

The gnostic component includes the study of the content and methods of influencing other people, taking into account the age of employees, individual characteristics, characteristics of the educational process and the results of their work, its advantages and disadvantages. On this basis, the activity of the leader Yu.V. Temaskin is being corrected and improved. Modern pedagogical technologies in preschool educational institutions. Year: 2012 ..

The head of the pre-school education organization carries out the completeness of administrative management. He assumes full responsibility for the work of the institution entrusted to him.

Selection of important issues and their thorough preparation for discussions at the meetings of the pedagogues' council and labor team, creation of a business environment, and coordination of team work largely depend on the leader.

Coordinated activities of administrative management at all levels, their interaction with collegial management bodies are highly effective in achieving the goals set for preschool education organization employees.

Thus, from the point of view of the regulation of preschool education, one of its main features is the important role of parents (legal representatives) in the process of organizing education and upbringing, in which preschool educational institutions have their own "additional" functions as a facilitating element in relation to the activities of parents as participants in the educational process.

As for the preschool educational organization, the state accreditation certificate has a special place, which confirms the state status of such an educational organization, the level and direction of the educational programs it implements. State accreditation of a pre-school educational organization or an additional educational organization for children requires an examination of the performance indicators of such an educational organization necessary to determine educational programs of the appropriate level and direction, as well as its type and category. includes transfer. Vinogradova, N.V. Miklyaeva "Formation of gender identity" Methodological guide Moscow, Creative Center SPHERE, 2012 ..

A special feature of preschool education is that providing medical care to students plays an important role in the activities of educational institutions, as well as in recreational activities. In fact, health workers act and should act as full participants in the educational process along with teachers, parents and students in the preschool educational organization.

At preschool age, there is a rapid development and reconstruction in the work of all physiological systems of the child's body: nervous, cardiovascular, endocrine, musculoskeletal system. The child's height and weight increase rapidly, body proportions change. There are significant changes in the higher nervous system. Preschool has a special place in the mental development of a young child: in this period of life, new psychological mechanisms of activity and behavior begin to form.

At this age, the foundations of the future personality are laid: a stable structure of motives is formed; new social needs appear (the need to respect and acknowledge adults, the desire to do

"adult" work that is important to others, to be "adults"; the need to recognize peers: preschool children are active in collective forms of activity are interested. and at the same time - games and other activities to be the first, the best; there is a need to act in accordance with established rules and ethical standards, etc.); a new (mediated) type of motivation appears - the basis of voluntary behavior; the child learns a certain system of social values; moral standards and rules of behavior in society, in some cases he can restrain his immediate desires and act not as he wants at the moment, but as "should" (I want to watch "cartoons", but my mother asks to play with her brother or go to the store; I don't want to put toys away, but this is the duty of the attendant, that is, it must be done, etc.).

Until the age of seven, the baby acts according to the experiences that belong to him at the moment. His desires and the expression of these desires in behavior (that is, internal and external) are an inseparable whole. The behavior of a child of this age can be conditionally described according to the scheme: "I wanted - I did it." Simplicity and spontaneity show that the child is the same from the outside as "inside", his behavior is understandable and easily "read" by others. Losing spontaneity and naivety in the behavior of a preschool teacher means introducing into his actions some intellectual moments that are connected between the child's experience and actions. His behavior remains conscious and can be described by another scheme: "wanted - realized - did." Therefore, they do not have a conscious desire to change.. A. Barannikova "About boys and girls, as well as their parents" Methodical guide Moscow, creative center SPHERE, 2012.

At preschool age, the child first of all understands the discrepancy between what position he occupies among other people and his real capabilities and desires. The desire to take a new, more "adult" position in life and to carry out new activities that are important not only for oneself, but also for other people is clearly expressed. The child, as it were, "falls out" from his usual life, and the pedagogical system applied to him loses interest in preschool education. In the context of universal school education, this is manifested, first of all, in the desire of children to acquire the social status of a student and learning as a new socially significant activity ("In school - adults, in kindergarten - only children"), as well as as in the desire to perform some other tasks of adults, to take on some of their obligations, to be a helper in the family.

The child begins to understand his place among other people, he develops his internal social position and the desire for a new social role that corresponds to his needs. The child begins to understand and generalize his experience, a stable self-esteem and an appropriate attitude towards success and failure in activities are formed (some are characterized by success and the pursuit of high achievements, while for others it is very important to avoid failures and unpleasant experiences).

In the process of development, the child develops not only an image of his own qualities and abilities (the embodiment of the real "I" - "who I am"), but also an idea of how he should be. how others want to see him (the image of the ideal "me" - "what I would like to be"). Congruence of the real "I" with the ideal is an important indicator of emotional well-being.

If we pay attention to the theoretical review of the scientific achievements of the scientists of our republic and foreign psychological-pedagogical science in the field of professional competence and competences, then a theoretical analysis of competent systematic approaches to the organization of the pedagogical process has been carried out. The analysis of researches in the

field of theoretical development and implementation of these approaches made it possible to reveal the essence of the problem we are studying through a detailed study of basic concepts such as "competence", "professional competence", "gender education".

The results of a sociological survey conducted among the leaders of pre-school education organizations in the Syrdarya region indicate that it is urgent to develop the professional competence of the bachelors of pedagogical education in the field of gender education. 77% of respondents indicated that they are ready to hire a young specialist with competence in gender education of preschool children.

The analysis of regulatory documents, socio-philosophical, pedagogical, psychological literature, the study of the work experience of pedagogues of preschool educational organizations, the analysis of the practice of introducing special courses on gender issues into the higher education system made it possible to identify a number of conflicts:

- **at the socio-psychological level**–The recognition of the gender approach by the United Nations Economic and Social Council in terms of "assessing the event in terms of its impact on women and men, including at the level of legislation, strategies and programs in all sectors" and its main ideas are that of the growing generation, particularly between insufficient use for effective socialization during preschool childhood;

- between recognition by the scientific community of gender socialization as the leader in the development of a person of a certain gender and underestimation of the impact of the professional competence of the bachelors of pedagogical education on this process;

- **at the scientific-theoretical level**– between the deep theoretical foundation of the phenomenon of professional competence in the context of humanitarian sciences (philosophy, sociology, psychology) and the insufficient development of the concept and structure of the professional competence of bachelors of pedagogical education in various fields of educational activity of preschool children, including gender;

- **at the scientific and methodological level** - between developments in the field of monitoring the process of gender education of the growing generation at various stages of the educational system of psychological and pedagogical science and the pedagogical practice of using these developments in the preparation of future bachelors of pedagogical education; between the real possibilities of using the resources of the higher education system for the development of professional competence in the field of gender education of preschool children and the lack of target orientations, content, technology and diagnostic tools for studying the characteristics of the organization of this process and its effectiveness.

The identified contradictions determine the relevance of the **problem** we are researching, and this problem consists in studying the essence of the phenomenon of professional competence of the bachelors of pedagogical education in the field of gender education of preschool children and finding ways to effectively develop it in the educational process at OO'YU.

Certain theoretical foundations (**conditions**) have emerged in science to solve the specified problem, and they have been reflected in philosophical, sociological, psychological and pedagogical works:

- the first group of works consists of research related to the images of men and women presented in the history of philosophical thought, the phenomenon of gender (A. Augustine, I.

Kant, J. J. Rousseau, K. G. Young, J. Baudrillard, M. Foucault); organizes researches devoted to characteristics of personality development in the polycultural educational space, defining culture as a factor of socialization of personality (P. Berger, I. E. Vidt, T. Lukman, M. Mead, A. V. Mudrik, R. M. Chumicheva);

- the second group of studies is connected with defining the characteristics of professional competence as a multifaceted phenomenon (N. M. Boritko, I. A. Zimnyaya, A. K. Markova, A. V. Khutorskoy);

- the third group includes studies reflecting the essence and uniqueness of gender socialization in preschool childhood (L. V. Gradusova, Yu. S. Grigor'yeva, L. V. Kolomiychenko, N. E. Tatarinseva), as well as personality integration, characteristics of the manifestation of gender characteristics of a person in society researches (O. Weynenger, D. V. Kolesov, A. Maslow, K. Rodgers) were included;

- the fourth group consists of studies based on the ideas of gender approach in higher education practice (L. N. Azarova, S. D. Matyushkova, O. V. Morozova, O. V. Prozumentik, A. A. Chekalina).

The legal documents indicating the relevance of the research problem, its fundamental theoretical foundations and the ways to solve it, allowed us to formulate the topic of our scientific research: "Improving the professional competence of future teachers in the gender education of children."

Conclusion/Recommendations. Thus, the most important and important period for gender development and education, socialization is preschool age. Therefore, it is necessary to properly organize the process of upbringing and education in the preschool educational organization and family, which will help to create favorable conditions for understanding interpersonal relationships in the future.

In conclusion, it should be noted that boys and girls cannot be raised in the same way. They feel, experience and perceive the world around them in different ways. Parents should follow gender education for preschool children. Thanks to this approach, girls become gentle, caring, understanding women who can comfort in difficult times, and boys become fearless, who can withstand all difficulties, protect loved ones and needy people in case of danger, become strong men.

REFERENCES

1. Tatarintseva N. O'g'il va qizlarning gender-rol ta'limi to'g'risida. "Maktabgacha ta'lim" 2009 yil 6-son.
2. Сальникова Ю.Н. Технология развития профессиональной компетентности бакалавров педагогического образования в области гендерного воспитания детей дошкольного возраста/Гендерный подход в гуманитарных исследованиях/ под.ред. А.Ю. Нагорновой. - Ульяновск, 2016 - 188 с.
3. Repina T.A. Bolalarning jinsiy-rol sotsializatsiyasi muammosi. Moskva: Moskva psixologik va ijtimoiy instituti nashriyoti; Voronej: NPO "MODEK", 2004 yil.
4. Bujigeeva M.Yu. Ta'limning boshlang'ich bosqichida bolalarning gender xususiyatlari // Pedagogika. - 2002 yil.

5. Qodirova F.R, Toshpo'latova SH.Q, A'zamova M.N. "Maktabgacha pedagogika" T.: Tafakkur, T-2019-yil
6. Jo'rayeva D.R. Maktabgacha ta'lim yoshidagi bolalarga ta'lim-tarbiya berishning zamonaviy tendensiyalari T.: 2015 y. O'zPFITI Uslubiy qo'llanma
7. education.com